

Anatomical Studies of Alfalfa Accessions under Normal and Stress

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Abstract

*Abiotic stresses have negative impact upon the plant growth and development. Among abiotic stresses salinity is the most widespread issue. It adversely affects the physiological activities of plants. Salt stress negatively affects alfalfa (*Medicago sativa L.*) production. Salt stress is one of the main environmental strains that effects the plants development and reduces the yield. Stress also affects the plants at cellular level because it causes toxicity. Pakistan is one of the major salt effected countries in the world. Salinity reduces seed germination rate. To investigate the salt stress tolerance among alfalfa morphological and yield related components an experiment was carried out in 2019-2020. The Research was conducted in complete randomized design by using exotic and indigenous four genotypes (V1, V2, V3 and V4) were grown under three salt stress treatment control (T_0) 5ml (T_1) 120ml (T_2) 140ml at research area of Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, University of Agriculture Faisalabad. Supply of different treatments of salt stress accelerated the seedling growth and increase tolerance in alfalfa to stress. The impacts of salt treatments on morphological traits (Germination percentage (%), Fresh root weight (g), Dry root weight (g), Fresh shoot weight (g), Dry shoot weight (g), Root length (cm), Shoot length (cm), Number of leaves, Fresh seedling weight (g), Dry seedling weight (g)) were analyzed by CRD, ANOVA factorial analysis and correlation-coefficient analysis. The information gained could be used in selection and breeding program aimed to improve alfalfa.*

Keywords: Seedling, Nitrogen fixation, Salt stress, Rhizobium symbiosis.

INTRODUCTION

Alfalfa is perennial flowering herb that called as lucerne. It is well known as queen of the forages. Relatively, alfalfa is high in protein and low in fiber contents as compared to other forages. Alfalfa is used in ayurvedic and homeopathic medicines. Alfalfa has good adaptability to different environmental conditions due to its variable genetic base and Due to its high nutritional quality. Alfalfa is one of the most important legume forages of the world.

Alfalfa is one of the best hybrid crop grown around the worldwide. It is cultivated in more than 80 countries with an area exceeding 35 million ha. After sorghum, alfalfa is the third most important crop in India and Pakistan in the world. Fodder crops are used as cheapest source for hay and livestock. Fodder crops are essential for nutrients and for development of livestock.

In the process of growth, plants are subjected to all kinds of biotic and abiotic stress. To cope with different stresses, plants have developed arrays of physiological and biochemical strategies to adapt to the adverse conditions. Soil salinity is one of the most significant abiotic stresses for crop plants. Salt tolerance is a complex trait involving responses to cellular osmotic and ionic stresses and their consequent secondary stresses and whole plant coordination.

Under salinity stress, a large number of proteins concerned with compartmentalization, regulation of gene expression and detoxification can be induced in plants. Sodium compartmentalization in vacuoles is one of the most important strategies that plant cells use to resist salt stress. Abundant researches had proven that accumulation of Na^+/H^+ antiporter in vacuolar membrane could dramatically improve plant salt tolerance.

Root nodules have a stronger antioxidant defense capacity than the host roots: higher amounts of antioxidant molecules (ascorbate, reduced glutathione, and homoglutathione and higher activities of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, catalase, peroxidases, and ascorbate-glutathione cycle enzymes. Therefore, plant-associated rhizobia can impart some degree of tolerance by plants to abiotic stresses (Grover *et al.*, 2011; Shrivastava and Kumar 2015).

Abiotic stresses have negative impact upon the plant growth and development. These are the non-living part of the environment that adversely impacts the plant. Among abiotic stresses salinity is the most widespread issue. Salinity is presence of excessive amount of soluble salts in water table or soil. It adversely affects the physiological activities of plants. It also reduces vascular tissues along with leaf density. Salt stress involves complex morphological trait, metabolic pathways, and gene regulation. Different researchers identified various responses to salinity stress at cellular, physiological and molecular level (Postnikova *et al.*, 2013). Pakistan is one of the major salt effected countries in the world. Salinity reduces seed germination rate and chlorophyll content, also causes nutritional imbalance (Yacoubi *et al.*, 2013). Alfalfa is a very important forage crops that is affected by salinity. It reduces seed germination; retardation in growth of alfalfa under salt stress, unfortunately extremely little work is done or, the anatomical study of alfalfa under salt stress. Therefore the present study is planned to anatomical studies of alfalfa accessions under normal and salt stress.

One adverse effect of salinity is the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as superoxide anion (O_2^-) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), inducing oxidative stress (Ertani *et al.* 2013). ROS not only damage host plants but also negatively affect nitrogen fixation (Becana *et al.*, 2000).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Research was conducted in Greenhouse of Department of plant breeding and Genetics, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. Three seeds of each genotype per replication was sown using Completely Randomize Design arrangement. Four genotypes with three replications was grown under three salt stress treatments i.e. control (T_0) 5ml (T_1) 120ml (T_2) 140ml. Polythene bags will be filled with soil and sand. 10 ml of distilled water was given to all polythen bags after three days. All agronomic practices was performed from sowing till germination. According to geographical map Faisalabad is present at longitude of 72-74 in East and latitude of 29-31 North and has 183m above sea level. The environmental conditions including temperature and soil are very suitable for alfalfa. weeds were uprooted with hand when necessary. Seedling growth was observed daily. Three plants of per genotypes per replication were selected randomly and tagged. Data was recorded of each genotype per replication. The impacts of salt treatments on morphological traits (Germination percentage (%), Fresh root weight (g), Dry root weight (g), Fresh shoot weight (g), Dry shoot weight (g), Root length (cm), Shoot length (cm), Number of leaves, Fresh seedling weight (g), Dry seedling weight (g)) were analyzed by CRD, ANOVA factorial analysis and correlation-coefficient analysis.

Plant growth and nodule formation

Plants were harvested before salt treatment for nodule examination as well as dry weight. Dry weight of shoots and roots was recorded after drying at 105 °C for 20 min and then at 70 °C to a constant weight. Alfalfa morphological traits were determined on a smple of three randomly collected plants of each tagged genotype from the center of the tubs when seed germinated. The plants were uproot and washed with tap water and blotted on tissue paper. After blotting the fresh weight of root, fresh shoot weight, fresh root weight, fresh seedling weight, was measured in grams with help of weight meter, at the same time Shoot length and number of leaves were also recorded. Then plants were kept in the oven for desiccaation. After few days plant were taken and the dry root weight, dry shoot weight, dry seedling weight was measured with the help of weight meter in grams. Some descriptive traits also recorded by visual representation.

Statistical analyses

The experiment was carried out in a factor factorial design with a completely randomized block layout. Three salt treatments (control (T_0) 5ml (T_1) 120ml (T_2) 140ml) used for determination of morphological and anatomical characters. Statistics(8.1) and R software was used for statistical analysis. Other data were subjected to analysis of variance and p value were compared using at the level of significance (defined as $\alpha= 0.05$). To explore the physiological responses of alfalfa leaf and root to nodulation under salt stress.

Results

The presence of sufficient genetic variability in our research material may be helpful for future breeding programs. Among the recorded traits the variability for germination (%), shoot length (cm), root length (cm), fresh root weight (g), fresh shoot weight (g), dry shoot weight (g), dry seed weight (g), fresh seed weight (g), number of leaves, dry root weight (g) ranged from 80.000-95.556, 14.822-16.089, 9.011-12.033, 1.5000 -1.6111, 1.8222-3.0556, 0.5100 - 1.0556, 1.1333-1.2667, 3.2000 -3.6222 and 9.333 -10.667, 1.2444-1.3111 respectively. By comparing the ranges reported in literature with ranges obtained our material could be considered valuable.

Rhizobium symbiosis can enhance ability of alfalfa to tolerate the salinity stress based on survival rate 140 mM NaCl treatment. However, our data also showed that V1 plants exhibited better shoot regrowth than V2, V3 and V4 under salinity.

Overall genotypic correlations were greater than phenotypic correlations.

The findings of this research explored that the supply of different treatments of salt stress accelerated the seedling growth and alfalfa showed tolerance to stress. NOL was significant and positive correlation with Drsw. G% was significant and positive correlation with FRW. SL was significant and positive correlation with FRW, DSW under treatment (T₀) 5ml. NOL was significant and positive correlation with G%, and FSW. G% was significant and positive correlation with NOL, SL significant and positive correlation with FSW, FSW significant and positive correlation with Drsw under treatment (T₁) 120ml. NOL was significant and positive correlation with DSW under treatment of (T₂) 140ml. The results indicated that by applying the different salt stresses on alfalfa genotypes V1, V2, V3 and V4. The genotype V1 revealed maximum positive results and showed high tolerance level against stress as compared to other three genotypes. This was demonstrated that these components are helpful to expand the forage yield under salt stress. This data would be useful about alfalfa and the determination of better genotypes for the improvement of alfalfa survival under salinity.

DISCUSSION

In this study we study the response of alfalfa growth under various salt treatments by assessing the survival rate and their ability to deal with oxidative and osmotic stress induced by salt. Salt stress negatively affects alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) production and biological nitrogen fixation and we were founded rhizobium symbiosis has an effect on host plant tolerance to salt stress.

Rhizobium symbiosis can enhance ability of alfalfa to tolerate the salinity stress based on survival rate 140 mM NaCl treatment. However, our data also showed that V1 plants exhibited better shoot regrowth than V2, V3 and V4 under salinity. There are may be two explanations for these results that salt tolerance may be supported by some active molecules that produce during stress and demand functional symbiosis. Second, parasitic nodules required energy and compete with host plants in response to salinity which may explain why other varieties performed worse under salt stress. In a study it was observed that soybean plants will sanction Rhizobium by limiting oxygen supply to the bacterium if rhizobium does not fix nitrogen (Kiers *et al.*, 2003).

Symbiosis adapted some responses after salt treatment, ROS formation is necessary phenomenon of aerobic respiration it showed symbiosis and nodulation affect the antioxidant response. ROS are incapable of enactment randomly to drive oxidative damage to bio molecules such as lipid peroxidation, denaturation of proteins, and mutation of DNA (Porcel *et al.*, 2012). Common ROS include O₂⁻, H₂O₂, and hydroxyl free radical (OH) (Gill and Tuteja 2010). Plants accumulate proline, soluble sugar, and stress responsive proteins that participate actively in the osmotic adjustment when plants are under salt stress (Evelin *et al.*, 2009).

Correlation coefficient analysis examined among morphological traits of alfalfa under three different treatments control T₀, T₁ and T₂. was highly significant and positive correlation with dry seed weight, Germination%, fresh shoot weight and dry shoot weight under salt stress treatments (T₁) 120ml, 5ml (T₂), control (T₀) 140ml respectively. Dry seed weight, number of leaves, germination%, number of seeds per inflorescence had the highest positive correlations with seed yield per plant as reported by (Aguillar *et al.*, 2002). The same traits were found to have the highest correlation with number of leaves in the research reported here (Table 3,4).

Germination %

Graphical representation of morphological traits of different alfalfa genotypes

Root length

Fresh root weight

Fresh shoot weight

Dry shoot weight

Dry seed weight

Fresh seed weight

shoot length

Number of leaves

Dry root weight

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Table. 1 Genotypic correlation among traits of alfalfa under treatment (T₀)

	G%	SL	RL	FRW	FSW	DSW	Drsw	Fsw	NOL
G%	1.000								
SL	-0.3813	1							
RL	0.3319	0.4541	1						
FRW	0.6064*	0.6360*	0.5457	1					
FSW	-0.7384**	-0.1276	-0.1037	-0.9735**	1				
DSW	-0.9093**	0.8802**	0.09708	-0.0379	0.3857	1			
Drsw	-0.5000	0.2701	-0.7927**	0.0568	-0.1759	0.5397	1		
Fsw	0.3550	-0.8493**	0.0694	-0.5835*	0.3910	-0.7572**	-0.7302**	1	
NOL	-0.7303*	-0.5918*	-1.2430**	-0.8304**	0.4297	0.0808	0.9128**	-0.0353	1.000

SL: shoot length, **RL:** root length, **FRW :** Fresh root weight, **FSW:** Fresh shoot weight, **DSW:** Dry Shoot weight, **Fsw:** Fresh seed weight

NOL: Number of leaves , **G%:** germination percentage, **Drsw:** Dry seed weight

Table. 2 Phenotypic correlation among traits of alfalfa under treatment (T₀)

	G%	SL	RL	FRW	FSW	DSW	Drsw	Fsw	NOL
G%	1.000								
SL	-0.3526	1							
RL	0.3161	0.4188	1						
FRW	0.4815	0.3820	0.3904	1					
FSW	-0.6766**	-0.1957	-0.14799	-0.7675**	1				
DSW	-0.7449**	0.7121**	-0.0527	-0.0352	0.3043	1			
Drsw	-0.4714	0.2077	-0.6666**	-0.0851	-0.0897	0.3530	1		
Fsw	0.3541	-0.7863**	0.0685	-0.4709	0.3666	-0.6427*	-0.6830	1	
NOL	-0.3960	-0.2269	-0.7411**	-0.5721*	0.3831	0.1633	0.5134	0.0095	1.000

SL: shoot length, **RL:** root length, **FRW :** Fresh root weight, **FSW:** Fresh shoot weight, **DSW:** Dry Shoot weight, **Fsw:** Fresh seed weight

NOL: Number of leaves , **G%:** germination percentage, **Drsw:** Dry seed weight

Table. 3 Genotypic correlation among traits of alfalfa under treatment (T₁)

	G%	SL	RL	FRW	FSW	DSW	Drsw	Fsw	NOL
G%	1.000								
SL	-0.20268	1							
RL	-0.15669	0.57525	1						
FRW	-0.61546*	1.04727	1.3958	1					
FSW	0.24133	0.67499**	-0.22882**	-0.06325	1				
DSW	-0.94636**	0.12682	-0.38396	0.08817	0.00112	1			
Drsw	-0.20751	0.39008	-0.68397	-0.28098	0.82336**	0.5351	1		
Fsw	-0.22518	-0.58097*	0.39126	0.07036	-1.01014**	-0.06948	-0.88303**	1	
NOL	0.7462**	-0.01223	-0.69143	-0.79386**	0.72573**	-0.41741	0.5137	-0.77182**	1.000

SL: shoot length, **RL:** root length, **FRW :** Fresh root weight, **FSW:** Fresh shoot weight, **DSW:** Dry Shoot weight, **Fsw:** Fresh seed weight

NOL: Number of leaves , **G%:** germination percentage, **Drsw:** Dry seed weight

Table. 4 Phenotypic correlation among traits of alfalfa under treatment (T₁)

	G%	SL	RL	FRW	FSW	DSW	Drsw	Fsw	NOL
G%	1.000								
SL	-0.1915	1							
RL	-0.0990	0.5254	1						
FRW	-0.2901	0.6203*	0.6287*	1					
FSW	0.2286	0.5849*	-0.2245	0.0847	1				
DSW	-0.8818**	0.1466	-0.0547	0.1859	0.5431**	1			
Drsw	-0.2075	0.3687	-0.4322	-0.1324	0.7801**	0.4986	1		
Fsw	-0.2128	-0.4780	0.3351	0.1567	-0.9526**	-0.0393**	-0.8348	1	
NOL	0.7035**	-0.0654	-0.5109	-0.5132	0.6686**	-0.4382	0.4843	-0.7060**	1.000

SL: shoot length, **RL:** root length, **FRW :** Fresh root weight, **FSW:** Fresh shoot weight, **DSW:** Dry Shoot weight, **Fsw:** Fresh seed weight

NOL: Number of leaves , **G%:** germination percentage, **Drsw:** Dry seed weight

Table. 5 Genotypic correlation among traits of alfalfa under treatment (T₂)

	G%	SL	RL	FRW	FSW	DSW	Drsw	Fsw	NOL
G%	1.000								
SL	0.30037	1							
RL	0.8626**	0.7889**	1						
FRW	0.2153	-0.8257**	-0.1425	1					
FSW	0.7174**	-0.26586	0.2455	0.2451	1				
DSW	0.7492**	-0.06963	1.2302	0.8696**	-0.54858	1			
Drsw	0.7620**	0.40452	0.4087	-0.4082	0.95185**	-0.3873	1		
Fsw	0.7602**	0.7839**	0.7541**	-0.5477	0.56757*	0.0577	0.8944**	1	
NOL	-0.6816**	-0.34841	-0.2348	0.4868	-1.02197	0.6062*	-0.9938**	-0.8444**	1.000

SL: shoot length, **RL:** root length, **FRW :** Fresh root weight, **FSW:** Fresh shoot weight, **DSW:** Dry Shoot weight, **Fsw:** Fresh seed weight

NOL: Number of leaves , **G%:** germination percentage, **Drsw:** Dry seed weight.

Table. 6 Phenotypic correlation among traits of alfalfa under treatment (T₂)

	G%	SL	RL	FRW	FSW	DSW	Drsw	Fsw	NOL
G%	1.000								
SL	0.1697	1							
RL	0.5963*	0.4806	1						
FRW	0.1928	-0.5669*	0.2618	1					
FSW	0.5115	-0.1634	-0.3288	-0.1932	1				
DSW	0.1471	0.4208	0.5085	0.3249	-0.3465	1			
Drsw	0.7324**	0.3347	0.2971	-0.3110	0.6689**	-0.1740	1		
Fsw	0.7307**	0.6486*	0.5481	-0.4173	0.3988	0.0259	0.8944**	1	
NOL	-0.6313*	-0.2632	-0.2208	0.3057	-0.6458*	0.2481	-0.9829**	-0.8352**	1.000

SL: shoot length, **RL:** root length, **FRW :** Fresh root weight, **FSW:** Fresh shoot weight, **DSW:** Dry Shoot weight, **Fsw:** Fresh seed weight

NOL: Number of leaves , **G%:** germination percentage, **Drsw:** Dry seed weight